

University of Warsaw
Faculty of "Artes Liberales"
Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA)
and The Cluster: The Past for the Present

International Conference
Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
May 22–25, 2024

ERC Proof of Concept Grant (101122976)

The Modern Argonauts

A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People
for Contemporary Challenges
through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology

The Conference Programme

May 22, 2024 (Wednesday)

Ball Room, Tyszkiewicz-Potocki Palace, University of Warsaw, Krakowskie Przedmieście 32

10.00 Opening of the Conference

Introduction: **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw

- ▣ **Robert A. Sucharski**, Dean of the Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw

10.30–12.00 European Research Council (ERC) Panel

Moderator: **Jerzy Axer**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw

- ▣ **Aneta Barkley**, European Research Council Executive Agency, Project Adviser
- ▣ **Véronique Dasen**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, Principal Investigator of the ERC Advanced Grant “Locus Ludi” (741520)
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw, Principal Investigator of the ERC Consolidator Grant “Our Mythical Childhood” (681202) and of the ERC Proof of Concept Grant “The Modern Argonauts” (101122976)
- ▣ **Anna Demner**, University of Warsaw Office for International Research and Liaison
- ▣ **Session Q&A**

12.00–12.30 Coffee break and time for the ERC-related talks and consultations

12.30–12.45 Sonya Nevin, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, and **Steve K. Simons**, Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Animating the Ancient World for the Modern Argonauts Educational Programme*

12.45–13.00 Irene Di Gioia and **Ippolita Giannotta**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna and Department of Philosophy, University of Göttingen, *A Mythical Quiz: How to Test the Outcome of the Lessons*

13.00–13.45 The Gods’ Playground

Moderator: **Markus Janka**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich

- ▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine “Lente”, *Meet Atlas*
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Prometheus*
- ▣ **Lisa Maurice** and **Ayelet Peer**, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University, *Meet Deucalion and Pyrrha*

14.00 Lunch for Speakers and time for the ERC-related talks and consultations

15.30–17.00 Women's Mythical Agency

Moderator: **Lisa Maurice**, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University

▣ **Katarzyna Jerzak**, Krieger School of Arts and Sciences, Johns Hopkins University, *Meet Eros and Psyche*

▣ **Oksana Ruchynska**, Department of Ancient and Medieval History, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University and Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, and **Alfred Twardecki**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and Institute for History of Material Culture, Polish Academy of Sciences, *Meet the Amazons*

▣ **Véronique Dasen**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, and **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Meet Atalanta*

▣ **Véronique Dasen**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, and **Krzysztof Korwin-Piotrowski**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and ORFEO Foundation, *Meet Kallisto*

▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Meet the Sirens*

17.00–17.15 Coffee break

17.15–18.45 Beyond Colchis

Moderator: **Katarzyna Jerzak**, Krieger School of Arts and Sciences, Johns Hopkins University

▣ **David Movrin**, Department of Classics, University of Ljubljana, *Meet the Dragons*

▣ **Tajinder Kaur**, Department of Anthropology, University of Delhi, and **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Meet Indrani and Iris*

▣ **Ariko Kato**, School of World Liberal Arts, Nagoya University of Foreign Studies, *Meet Kamuy*

▣ **Eleanor A. Dasi**, **Divine Che Neba**, and **Daniel A. Nkemleke**, Ecole Normale Supérieure, University of Yaoundé I, *Learn of the Origin of the Dry and Rainy Seasons*

▣ **Mai Musié**, Swansea University and University of Oxford, *Meet Perseus and Andromeda*

19.00 Dinner for Speakers and time for the ERC-related talks and consultations

May 23, 2024 (Thursday)

Columned Hall, Faculty of History Building, University of Warsaw, Krakowskie Przedmieście 26/28

9.30 Maria Wiśniewska, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Learning Leadership through Mythology*

9.45–10.30 Schools Session: Reports on the Lessons Testing

- ▣ **Barbara Strycharczyk's Class**, "Strumienie" High School in Józefów
- ▣ **Anna Wojciechowska's Class**, Mikołaj Rej XI High School in Warsaw

10.30–11.00 Faculty of "Artes Liberales" Students' Presentations, *Mythology Just Around the Corner*

11.00–11.30 Coffee break

11.30–12.15 Prolegomena

Moderator: **Elżbieta Olechowska**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW

▣ **Helen Lovatt**, Department of Classics, University of Nottingham, *The Myth of the Argonauts*

- ▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Know Your Name*
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Our Mythical Template*

12.15–13.00 The Future Routes of the Modern Argonauts

Moderator: **Oksana Ruchynska**, Department of Ancient and Medieval History, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University and Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg

▣ **Kerttu Männiste**, Kadriorg Art Museum in Tallinn, Art Museum of Estonia, *The Modern Argonauts Programme and Ovid at the Kadriorg Art Museum 2025 Exhibition*

▣ **Davide Ingo**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Pisa and Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW (Student Mobility Erasmus Traineeship), *The Italian Translation of a Choice of the Modern Argonauts Lessons*

▣ **Viktoriia Kotenko**, Institute of Archaeology, Ukrainian National Academy of Sciences, *A Report on Testing the Demeter and Persephone Lesson in the Lyceum No. 6 "Leader" of the Poltava City Council, Poltava, Ukraine*

13.00–13.15 Coffee break

13.15–14.00 Troy Story

Moderator: **David Movrin**, Department of Classics, University of Ljubljana

- ▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine "Lente", *Meet Laocoon*
- ▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine "Lente", *Meet Aeneas and Dido*
- ▣ **Sonja Schreiner**, Department of Classical Philology, Medieval and Neolatin Studies, University of Vienna, *Meet Achilles*

14.00 Lunch for Speakers

15.30–16.30 Navigare necesse est

Moderator: **Bridget Martin**, School of Classics, University College Dublin

▣ **Irene Di Gioia**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna and Department of Philosophy, University of Göttingen, *Meet Poseidon*

▣ **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Meet Odysseus and Penelope*

▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Cadmus and Europe*

16.30–17.30 A Mythical Tale of Crete

Moderator: **Krishni Burns**, College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, University of Illinois Chicago

▣ **Bettina Kümmerling-Meibauer**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Tübingen, *Meet Daedalus and Icarus*

▣ **Katarzyna Jerzak**, Krieger School of Arts and Sciences, Johns Hopkins University, *Meet Talos*

▣ **Krzysztof Rybak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Theseus and the Minotaur*

17.30–18.00 Coffee Break

18.00–19.00 Katabasis (and Back)

Moderator: **Bettina Kümmerling-Meibauer**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Tübingen

▣ **Bridget Martin**, School of Classics, University College Dublin, *Meet Hades*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska** and **Maria Wiśniewska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Demeter and Persephone*

▣ **Alfred Twardecki**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Institute for History of Material Culture, Polish Academy of Sciences, and **Krzysztof Korwin-Piotrowski**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and ORFEO Foundation, *Meet Orpheus and Eurydice*

▣ **Krzysztof Korwin-Piotrowski**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and ORFEO Foundation, *See Arcadia*

19.30 Dinner for Speakers

May 24, 2024 (Friday)

Conference Room, Collegium Artes Liberales (CLAS), Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, White Villa, Dobra 72

9.30–11.00 On Olympus

Moderator: **Caroline Bristow**, Cambridge School Classics Project, University of Cambridge

▣ **Owen Hodkinson**, Department of Classics, University of Leeds, *Meet Zeus and Hera*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Apollo*

- ▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Hephaestus*
- ▣ **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project,

Meet Ares

- ▣ **Elżbieta Olechowska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Dionysus*
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Hermes*

11.00–11.30 Coffee Break

11.30–13.00 The Divine Might of the Goddesses

Moderator: **Susan Deacy**, Department of Classics and Ancient History, University of Bristol

▣ **Amy Smith**, Department of Classics and Ure Museum of Greek Archaeology, University of Reading, and **Katerina Volioti**, Department of Humanities, University of Roehampton London, *Meet Aphrodite*

▣ **Krishni Burns**, College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, University of Illinois Chicago, and **Nava Cohen**, Department of Classics, Northwestern University, *Meet Hestia*

▣ **Krishni Burns**, College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, University of Illinois Chicago, and **Nava Cohen**, Department of Classics, Northwestern University, *Meet Athena*

▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine “Lente”, *Meet Artemis*

▣ **Caroline Bristow**, Cambridge School Classics Project, University of Cambridge, and *experta loci* **Kerttu Männiste**, Kadriorg Art Museum in Tallinn, Art Museum of Estonia, *Meet Actaeon*

13.00 Lunch for Speakers

14.00–15.30 The New Faces of Heroism

Moderator: **Amy Smith**, Department of Classics and Ure Museum of Greek Archaeology, University of Reading

▣ **Małgorzata Borowska** and **Przemysław Kordos**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Chiron*

▣ **Valentina Garulli**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, *Meet Asclepius*

▣ **Susan Deacy**, Department of Classics and Ancient History, University of Bristol, *Choose with Hercules*

▣ **Effrosyni Kostara**, Department of Education, Frederick University, *Meet Herakles (Labours)*

▣ **Hanna Paulouskaya**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Bellerophon and Pegasus*

15.30–15.45 Coffee Break

15.45–17.00 The Choices

Moderator: **Divine Che Neba**, Ecole Normale Supérieure, University of Yaoundé I

▣ **Raimund Fichtel**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, **Berkan Sariaydin**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, and **Maria Wiśniewska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet King Midas*

▣ **Frances Foster**, Faculty of Education, University of Cambridge, *Archaeology and Mythology: Animating a Composite Midas*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet the Sphinx*

▣ **Arlene Holmes-Henderson**, Department of Classics and Ancient History, Durham University, and *experta loci* **Alexandra Saz Peñamaria**, Interdisciplinary Research Group on Education, University of Andorra, *Meet Narcissus and Echo*

17.30 Dinner for Speakers

19.30 Concert in the Warsaw Philharmonic for Speakers

May 25, 2024 (Saturday)

Conference Room, Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA), Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, Zamoyski Palace, Nowy Świat 69

9.30–10.30 The Song Weavers

Moderator: **Ariko Kato**, School of World Liberal Arts, Nagoya University of Foreign Studies

▣ **Babette Puetz**, School of Languages and Cultures, Victoria University of Wellington – Te Herenga Waka, *Meet the Pleiades*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Calypso*

▣ **Hanna Paulouskaya**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Electra*

▣ **Maria Pia Napolitano de Majo**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, and *expertus loci* **Jean Krier**, Musée National d’Archéologie, d’Histoire et d’Art (MNAHA), Luxembourg, *Meet the Muses*

10.30–11.30 The Identity Quests

Moderator: **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project

▣ **Elizabeth Hale**, School of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences, University of New England, *Meet Circe*

▣ **Pietro Rosa**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna and Liceo Classico Statale Marco Minghetti, Bologna, and **Renzo Tosi**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, *Meet Medea*

▣ **Markus Janka**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, and **Michael Stierstorfer**, Gymnasium Kloster Schäftlarn, *Meet Medusa*

11.30–12.00 Coffee Break

12.00–12.30 To the Edge of the World

Moderator: **Effrosyni Kostara**, Department of Education, Frederick University

▣ **Elżbieta Olechowska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, and *expertus loci* **Adrian-Mario Gellel**, Faculty of Education, University of Malta, *See Atlantis*

▣ **Rachel Bryant Davies**, School of Languages, Linguistics and Film, Queen Mary University of London, *See the Isles of the Blessed*

12.30 Summary of the Conference, incl. the discussion on the next stages of the work on the Handbook

Moderator: **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW

13.00 Lunch for Speakers

16.00–19.00 Guided Visit to the Royal Łazienki Museum – mythology in the public space and the potential of *The Modern Argonauts Handbook* in museum lessons and workshops

20.00 Farewell dinner for Speakers

For more see: <https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/>

This Project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101122976, *The Modern Argonauts: A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People for Contemporary Challenges through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology*, ERC Proof of Concept Grant (2023–2025).

For the conference materials see:

<https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/conference>

Cover images by Matylda Tracewska and Steve K. Simons.

